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Editors

Dr. Amol Gawande

Dr. Atul Kumar

Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School

Tathawade, Mumbai Bangalore Highway

Pune 411033, Maharashtra, India

A STUDY OF THE ADVERSE EFFECTS OF SHOPPING ONLINE

Atul Kumar, Harshita Tak, Shubham Potdar

Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School

E mail: shubham.potdar.dypbs@gmail.com

Abstract:

Due to Corona pandemic all sectors of businesses shifted to online platforms, for their survival. Increased level of online shopping was seen due to imposed lockdowns and social distancing. Online shopping has number of advantages but there are certain disadvantages associated with the same and hence it's important to be cognizant of such consequences. Cheating and frauds are the major concern of online buying and hence awareness should be created amongst the online shoppers.

The study aims at exploring the disadvantages of online shopping. 120 respondents were surveyed from the city of Pune to collect their view about the disadvantages of online shopping.

Keywords: *Online buying, Advantages, Disadvantages*

1. Introduction:

The mode of shopping has seen a massive change due to Covid-19 crisis. The encouragement given to digital payments has also resulted in increased online purchase behavior. Increased convenience associated with online shopping such as decreased efforts and time, access to wide range of products, knowledge about discounts and ability to compare prices etc. But disadvantages especially cheating and fraud is a point of concern. This research article aims at finding the disadvantages of online shopping by knows their views regarding the same.

2. Methodology:

120 online customers were surveyed from the city of Pune. The questions dealt with identifying the hassles they faced while purchasing the products/services online. The questionnaire was prepared on 5 point Likert scale and the responses collected were validated for checking the reliability of the questionnaire on the basis of Cronbach's alpha score. The score was found to 0.821 which indicated that the questionnaire is reliable.

3. Data analysis and interpretation:

From the respondents 51 were male while 69 were females. 58 respondents were <40 years of age, 32 were between 40-50 years and 30 respondents were of the age >50 years.

The p value recorded was 0.007 which is <0.05 hence the null hypothesis that the factors stated are not the major disadvantages was rejected.

4. Conclusion:

While there are advantages to buying online, there are some drawbacks to buying online. This was based on an overwhelming agreement with statements such as – delivery and delay issues, fraud and fraud risk, and ultimately spending a lot of time online, it's with society and the community. Reduce contact, we may not know exactly what we are getting, there may be problems with returns, some websites are complicated and unfriendly, personal No sales support, problems with internet connectivity and speed, which leads to unemployment for locals and small retailers. Online buyers should be aware of these restrictions and be careful when making online purchases.

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ABOUT THE CONFERENCE

“Next Normal” is the latest buzzword two years after the Covid -19 pandemic hit all the sections of society and the economy. With the havoc now seemingly showing the downturn, it's the “Next to Normal” that will define 2022 and the subsequent years. Covid-19 has changed the world, society, and business function. With the Next Normal, the future demands resilience. Resilience is the CEO agenda of every company and across all industries. Businesses are reconsidering their approaching order to make it more resilient. Re-evaluating one's supply base, geographical footprint, moving with speed to digitize the operations end to end, encouraging flexibility to create new value for the customers, and increasing competitive advantage are certain considerations that need to be undertaken to build a resilient ecosystem for economic growth in the Next Normal. The 'Next Normal' also calls for innovative ways to re-engage an organization's human resources and marketing techniques. Other measures such as financial assistance, devising a favorable environment for the growth of startups, and regional collaboration among ecosystem developers can play an essential role in transforming the way businesses work are the other factors business leaders should consider as they prepare for “The Next Normal.” There is a need for in-depth scientific reflection regarding the methods and instruments for economic development in theoretical and practical terms. In this background, the prime goal of this Conference is to be a platform for discussing scientific achievements and evaluate the current state of research development on the role of institutional, financial, and technological innovation in fostering a resilient business ecosystem and economic growth.

ABOUT US

Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School runs AICTE approved PGDM program. It has been ranked 1st Emerging B-School among top institutes of west India by Times of India. It has also been conferred the ET Now Business School of the Year award. The two-year full-time PGDM program offered by Dr. D.Y. Patil B-School is designed to empower students to become successful business professionals in the challenging global scenario. The Institute is continually evolving to meet its goals in an ever-changing business environment. It has been playing an important role in professionalizing Indian management through its programs. Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School aims to create value-driven leaders, global managers and entrepreneurs with strong conceptual foundations and analytical approach to help them be the best in whichever field they choose. The aim is to innovatively address the needs of a modern India and connecting aspirations and realities to attain benchmarks that are respected internationally.

Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School

Sr. No. 87-88, Bengaluru-Mumbai Express Bypass,
Tathawade, Pune - 411033, Maharashtra, India

Contact No. : 8007989201

Email : info.bschool@dpu.edu.in

Website : www.bschool.dpu.edu.in